
LISTENING TO DIFFERENT ENGLISH VARIETIES AND ACCENTS

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Annotation: This study investigates how well English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners report understanding (i.e. comprehensibility) and actually understand (i.e. intelligibility) native and non-native accents of English, and how EFL learners' self-reported ease of understanding and actual understanding of these accents are aligned. Thirty-three Dutch-speaking EFL learners performed a comprehensibility and accentedness judgement task, followed by an orthographic transcription task. The judgement task elicited listeners' scalar ratings of authentic speech from eight speakers with traditional Inner, Outer and Expanding Circle accents. The strength of a speaker's accent significantly affected listeners' comprehensibility ratings. Most speakers were highly intelligible, with transcription accuracy ranging between 79% and 95%. The study foregrounds the effect of native and non-native accents on comprehensibility and intelligibility, and highlights the importance of multidialectal listening skills.

Key words: Different accents, comprehensibility, listener's scalar, intelligibility, multidialectal listenings skills, special attention, methodological relevance, based on speech, the flexibility of non-native phonological representations.

Listening in a second or foreign language is more difficult than listening in a first or native language. Even highly proficient foreign language learners may find

it arduous to listen to the non-native language they have been learning for many years . Several reasons lie at the heart of this difficulty, some of which are related to the inherent nature of listening: speech is fast, continuous and fleeting, meaning that listeners cannot go back and listen again, in the same way as they can reread a written passage . Additional difficulties may arise when there is background noise or when the speaker has an unfamiliar (regional or non-native) accent . Background noise and unfamiliar speaker accents are considered to contribute to the creation of ‘non-optimal’ conditions for listening, which may result in, for instance, increased processing effort. Varieties of English :

- British English: Includes accents such as Received Pronunciation (RP), Cockney, Scouse (Liverpool), Geordie (Newcastle), and West Midlands.

- American English: Features regional accents like Southern, New York, Midwestern, and Californian.

- Canadian English: Often similar to American English but has distinct pronunciations and vocabulary (e.g., “about” pronounced more like “about”).

- Australian English: Characterized by its unique slang and vowel shifts.

- New Zealand English: Similar to Australian but with distinct differences in pronunciation and vocabulary.

- Indian English: Influenced by local languages and dialects, often featuring a rhythmic intonation. These are opposed to ‘ideal’ listening conditions, that is when speech is produced in a quiet environment in a familiar accent. Most research on speech perception and intelligibility has used read speech or speech elicited in the laboratory, but nascent research is increasingly using unscripted, casual speech to examine how non-optimal listening conditions may complicate speech understanding. In line with this ongoing trend, the current study isolates speaker accents as one of the complicating factors for listening and examines how natural, unscripted speech produced in authentic contexts affects L2 speech perception and comprehension.

The International Dialects of English Archive (or IDEA) is a website with a huge amount of recordings from all over the world. IDEA recorded people reading a short story that was written specifically for hearing the different ways people pronounce sounds in the English language. On IDEA, you can listen to dialects by country, residence (where someone lives), gender or age. You can hear native English speakers of all kinds. You can even hear how someone sounds when they're born in one place but move to a different place later. Browse around and learn about all the wonderful ways people speak English! The Dialect Blog looks at how people speak in areas of America, England and Ireland. You can find a specific area you're interested in and find out what kind of dialect that area has. The explanations may be difficult to understand for anyone who isn't a linguist (someone who studies languages), but it's a great place to find out what makes each dialect different. For example, you can learn that people from New England (the Northeastern states of America) often don't pronounce the "r" sound at the ends of words. So the word "car" sounds more like "cah." The blog also has links to examples of the accents in use, so you can hear the differences between all the dialects. To hear many different English dialects, FluentU has real media clips from many English-speaking countries. FluentU takes real-world videos—like music videos, movie trailers, news and inspiring talks—and turns them into personalized language learning lessons.

It uses a natural approach that helps you ease into the English language and culture over time. You'll learn English as it's spoken in real life.

Conclusion: In the current study we set out to map the multidialectal listening skills of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners enrolled at a Flemish higher education institute. Specifically, we have determined the comprehensibility and intelligibility of various accents of English to non-native listeners, and the extent to which their self-reported ease of understanding and their actual understanding of native and non-native accented English are aligned.

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